

**INTERNATIONAL JOURNAL OF
PHARMACEUTICAL SCIENCES**
[ISSN: 0975-4725; CODEN(USA): IJPS00]
Journal Homepage: <https://www.ijpsjournal.com>

Research Article

Formulation And Evolution of The Herbal Night Cream (Golden Era)

Devram Sodha*

Gyanmanjari Pharmacy College, Bhavnagar-364001, Gujarat, India.

ARTICLE INFO

Published: 14 April. 2025

Keywords:

Brightening Effect, Herbal Cream, Glowing Skin, Pharmacology of Cream.

DOI:

10.5281/zenodo.15209472

ABSTRACT

The present study focuses on the formulation and evaluation of an herbal night cream, named Golden Era, using naturally derived ingredients with known dermatological benefits. The formulation includes turmeric extract, olive oil, lavender oil, vitamin E, rose water, beeswax, and borax. These ingredients were selected for their combined properties, including anti-inflammatory, antioxidant, antimicrobial, moisturizing, and skin-brightening effects. The cream was prepared using a simple emulsification method and tested for multiple parameters including patch testing, moisturization, brightening effect, anti-aging properties, and stability. The results demonstrated excellent skin compatibility, significant improvement in skin brightness, hydration, and elasticity, and a high level of user satisfaction. The formulation retained its stability and efficacy over a six-month observation period, suggesting its potential as a natural alternative in skincare applications.

INTRODUCTION

The golden Era is a night cream that has the natural ingredients for example olive oil ,Lavender oil ,vitamin E oil, turmeric extract (curcumin) rose water these are all the naturally we can extract for the experiment. Comment purpose of the cream is to blow up the skin naturally to not harm the skin. Now we can see the properties of all the use ingredient in the cream.

Pharmacology:

1) Lavender oil

Lavender oil is a volatile essential oil that can extract from *lavandula angustifolia*.

A) Chemical properties

Camphor - provide mild analgesic effect.

Linalyl - it provide anti inflammatory and sodium affected to the skin.

Linalool – linalool as the anti microbial properties and it provide calming effect.

B) Biological properties

*Corresponding Author: Devram Sodha

Address: Gyanmanjari Pharmacy College, Bhavnagar-364001, Gujarat, India.

Email : sodhadevang54@gmail.com

Relevant conflicts of interest/financial disclosures: The authors declare that the research was conducted in the absence of any commercial or financial relationships that could be construed as a potential conflict of interest.

Anti-microbial properties - to reduce the growth of the bacteria and fungi.

Anti-inflammatory properties - it reduce the inflammation

C) Cosmetic use of Lavender oil

It use for the skin care to burns , acne etc.

2) Olive oil

The olive oil is extracted from the fruit of olea europeea.

A) Chemical properties

Olic acid - good for heart health

Linoleic acid - provide Omega 6 fatty acid

Palmitic acid – provide texture and stability to cream

B) Biological properties

Heart healthy - reduce the bad cholesterol level (LDL) and increase good cholesterol level (HDL).

Anti microbial - reduction of the bacterial infections.

C) Cosmetic use of olive oil

In skin care – provide hydration to skin.

In hair care - increase the scalp health and hair.

In food industry - it has the quality fats.

3) Turmeric extract (curcumin)

A) Chemical properties of curcumin - it has anti inflammatory, antioxidant, and also has anti cancer properties.

B) Biological properties

Anti inflammatory - introduce the pain.

Wound healing - it is the wound.

Brightening effect - provide brightening effect of a skin.

C) Cosmetic use of turmeric

Skin care - use in the cream to brightening and glowing the skin.

Food - use to the natural colour.

4) Vitamin E

The vitamin E is the use of for the health of a skin. It has founded in the nuts and seeds etc.

A) Chemical properties

Alpha, beta, gamma and delta tocopherols - used to provide the protection of a skin.

B) Biological properties

Skin protection - protects from sunburn, aging, reduce scars

Immune booster - it helps to enhance the immunity.

C) Cosmetic use of vitamin E

Skin care - to reduce the aging, protection of the skin, moisturizing skin.

Food industry - it is used for the preservation of the processed foods.

5) Rose water

The rose water is the natural aromatic liquid. It is a widely used in cosmetics.

A) Chemical properties

Flavonoids - anti inflammatory and anti aging.

Nerol - used to hydration of a skin.

Geraniol - provide soothing effect.

B) Biological properties

Anti-inflammatory - reduce the inflammation.

Anti-aging - reducing the aging time.

Hydrating - hydrate the skin.

C) Cosmetic use of rose water

Skin care - for hydration, soothing and glowing effect.

Food - use in syrups as a flavours and for cooling effect.

6) Bees wax

Beeswax is the natural wax produced by honeybees (*Apis mellifera*). The main use of beeswax is for the provided texture of a cream, wound healing, antibacterial properties, emollient action etc.

7) Borax

Borax is mainly used for the emulsifying agent, here the mainly used in emulsifying water and oil phase.

METHODOLOGY:

At the starting of experiment we have the essential tools and the materials.

Chemicals: olive oil, Lavender oil, rose water, vitamin E, turmeric extract, bees wax, borax.

Apparatus used: double boiler, motor pastel, beakers, measuring cylinders, weight balance, glass rod etc.

METHOD:

Firstly we take 10 gram of bees wax (white bees wax) And then put the beaker on started boiler and set the beaker on it for melting the bees wax. Instead of this take 1.6 gram of borax add into another beaker and take 30 ml of rose water and add the borax and mixed it well. Stir the solution till it dissolve in the borax. Then add the turmeric powder (1.2g) After melting the bees wax in motor and pastel add bees wax in motor and then add olive oil drop by drop and mixed well with pastel. Completion of adding the olive oil and the solution of borax, rose water and turmeric powder it is also add drop by drop and mixed well. It seems like creamy texture add 2 to 4 drops of the vitamin E oil and mixed with pastel, then for the lavender oil drops of 2 to 4 drops. Mixed as follows step to form the perfect cream.

Caution: Stir continuous in the one direction to avoid the slum formation.

Testing of a night cream:

Here various test are performed,

1) Patch test:

Take the cream and apply on hand or foot to check the irritation problem. We done 24 hours of the patch test apply on hand and we not found any type of irritation on the skin.

2) Moisturization and hydration:

Taqreem has vitamin E and rose water that are mainly used to provide soothing effect and hydrate the skin. With the patch test we can find out it moisturize the skin and provide hydration to the skin.

3) Brightening skin tone test:

Turmeric is a well known for its ability to enhance the skin radiance and promote an even complexion. To assess this before and after study was conducted using detailed photographs and colour metre to check skin tone variations in Hindi videos with pigmentation concerns participants applied the cream (night cream) consistently for 4 weeks.

Results: after the month of use the cream 80% of participants noticed a visible improvement in their skin brightness. With the use of calorimeter we see 15 to 20% reduction in dark spots and pigmentation.

4) Anti-inflammatory effect:

For the assess of anti-inflammatory properties of night cream remainly use the turmeric and Lavender oil that are known for the calming and anti-inflammatory effects. Participants applied the night cream for two weeks. After skin condition was assessed using a visioscan which measures skin redness and inflammation.

Results: the party se pant has significant reduction in redness and inflammation after using one week of night cream, for the soothing of the skin Lavender oil and turmeric plays key role.

5) Anti aging evolution:

Vitamin E and olive oil are non for their antioxidant properties. Which are help to reduce

the aging and these is the key benefits of the cream. (Reduce the wrinkle). We selected the participant with visual wrinkles and we use 3D skin imaging to assess changes in skin texture. After using a week of the cream show results.

Results: after 1 month of using the night cream 75% participant experienced a noticeable reduction of the wrinkles. That the 3D skin imaging confirmed and improvement in skin elasticity.

6) User satisfaction survey:

After we conducted the 4 weeks of testing we survey the user satisfaction. (About effectiveness, texture, fragrance and all)

Results:

90% of participants says there skin looked more radiant and hydrated.

85% of participant notice and improvement in a skin texture.

70% of a participant experienced a reduction of redness and irritation.

95% satisfied with all the texture ,fragrance ,effectiveness.

7) Shelf life and stability testing:

To see the long term stability of the night cream with test its shelf life and stability by storing the cream under different conditions. For 6 months (we tested at condition in room temperature, in sunlight and in cool environment.

RESULTS:

The cream remain stable that is no separation or changes in colour or order during the 6 month period the ingredient specially vitamin E and

Lavender oil refined potent, confirm the effectiveness and quality over time.

CONCLUSION:

The Golden Era herbal night cream was successfully formulated using safe, natural, and effective ingredients with proven dermatological benefits. The evaluation results confirmed that the cream offers substantial advantages, including skin hydration, brightening, anti-aging, and anti-inflammatory effects. Notably, over 80% of participants observed visible improvements in skin tone and texture, and 95% expressed satisfaction with its fragrance, texture, and overall efficacy. Furthermore, the formulation exhibited excellent stability and maintained its integrity under varied environmental conditions. These findings support the potential of the Golden Era night cream as a reliable, natural skincare product that meets both therapeutic and cosmetic needs.

REFERENCES

1. Vishwakarma Bharat, Dwivedi Sumeet, Dubey Kushagra, and Joshi Hemant. Formulation And evaluation of herballipstick. *International Journal of Drug Discovery and Herbal Research*, 2011; 1(1): 18-19.
2. T Reynolds, AC Dweck. Aloe vera leaf gel: a review update. *J Ethno Pharmacol*, 1999;68: 3-37.
3. Priyanka Sharma, Amit C Kharkwal, Harsha Kharkwal, MZ Abdin, Ajit Varma. A review On the pharmacological properties of Aloe Vera. *Int J Pharm Sci Rev Res*, 2014; 29: 31-7.
4. Sharma Pankaj, Tomar Lokeshwar, Bachwani Mukesh, Bansal Vishnu. Review on neem (*Azadirachta indica*): thousand problems one solution. *Int Res J Pharm*, 2011; 2: 97-102.
5. KP Sampath Kumar, Debjit Bhowmik, Biswajit, Chiranjib, Pankaj, KK Tripathi Margret Chandira. Traditional Indian herbal plants Tulsi and its medical importance: a review. *Res Rev: J Pharmacogn Phytochem*, 2010; 2: 103-8.
6. Kalpesh Chhotalal Ashara. Importance of trituration technique on preparation and Evaluation of cold cream. *Inventi Rapid Pharm Tech*, 2013; 1-2: 2012.
7. Sk Uddandu Saheb, Aduri Prakash Reddy, K Rajitha, B Sravani, B Vanitha. Formulation And evaluation of cream from naturally containing plant extracts. *World J Pharm Pharm Sci*, 2018; 7: 851-62.
8. Mohammed Ali, textbook of pharmacognosy volume 1, page no 528, 676.
9. C. K. Kokate, A. P. Purohit, S. B. Gokhle, *Pharmacognosy*, NiraliPrakashan, 45th edition, Vol. 1, page no. 2. 1, 1. 113.
10. Vani mamillapalli, mounika katamanani, vamsimeghana tryyaggura, praneetha kanayam, Aslesha padmavadhi mumagiri, hariprya thondepu. Bhavani. Appikata-formulation, Phytochemical, physical evaluation of polyherbal vanishing cream and jacewash, volume 12 issue 03, research journal of pharmaceutical dosage form and technology, July-September 2020; 139-149.
11. Das K, Dang R, Machale MU, Ugandar RE, Lalitha BR. Evaluation for safety assessment of formulated vanishing cream containing aqueous Stevia extract for topical application. *Indian Journal of Novel Drug Delivery*, 2012; 4(1): 43-51.

HOW TO CITE: Devram Sodha*, Formulation and Evolution of The Herbal Night Cream (Golden Era), *Int. J. of Pharm. Sci.*, 2025, Vol 3, Issue 4, 1727-1731 <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15209472>

